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STAGE FEATURES OF KARABAKH-THEMED PERFORMANCES IN AZERBAIJANI THEATERS AFTER “VICTORY DAY”

Abstract. The article deals with the staging of works on the theme of Karabakh in Azerbaijani theaters after “Victory Day”. These performances were a source of people’s pride, igniting them with the love of building and creating more after the Victory Day. After the victory, the appreciation given to the martyrs, veterans and the families of the martyrs was told in the play “Zəfər yolu” (“Victory Road”) written and directed by Azer Pasha Nematov staged at the Azerbaijan State Academic National Drama Theater, the play “Bir nəfəs qədər” (“As Close As Breath”) written and directed by Samir Gulamov staged at the Azerbaijan State Academic Musical Theater, the play “Missiya” (“Mission”) written by Mubariz Hamidov and directed by Firudin Maharramov staged at the Sumgayit State Drama Theater, the play “Haqqın 44 günü” (“44 Days of Justice”) written and directed by Anar Babanlı at the Lankaran State Drama Theater, the play “Azad Şuşa” (“The Liberated Shusha”) by S. Ibrahimli in the production by Karim Hasanov staged at Aghdam State Drama Theater, the play “İlham ətirli Zəfər” (“Inspirational Victory”) by Rafiq Rahimli staged at Gusar State Lezgi Drama Theater.

Key words: theme of Karabakh, Patriotic War, Victory Day, historical victory, in memory of our martyrs

Introduction. The theme of Karabakh has always been relevant in theater art, and our theaters have turned to works on this theme before “Victory Day” and after “Victory Day”.

“Victory Road” by A.P.Nematov was staged Azerbaijan State Academic National Drama Theater(28.05.2022), “As Close As Breath” by S. Gulamov at the State Academic Musical Theater (09.11.2021), “Zəfər zəngi” (“Victory Bell”) by Z. Khalil at Azerbaijan State Puppet Theater named after A. Shaig (29.11.2022), “The Voice from Shusha” by N. Gadimli at Aghdam State Drama Theater (05.06.2023), “Mission” by M.Hamidov at Sumgayit State Drama Theater (10.11.2021),“44 Days of Justice” by A.Babanli at Lankaran State Drama Theater (16.09.2022), “Inspirational Victory” by R. Rahimli at Gusar State Lezgi Drama Theater (03.09.2022), etc.

The interpretation of the main material. The plays performed in the theaters of Azerbaijan showed our people’s spirit of victory and the desire to build and create after the Victory Day.The premiere of the play “As Close As Breath” written and directed by Samir Gulamov was held at the State Academic Musical Theater on November 9, 2021.

One of the works dedicated to the theme of Karabakh and Victory, the martyrs and veterans who gave us this joy and our proud mothers who brought them up is the play “Close as Breath” of the Azerbaijan State Academic Musical Theater.The premiere of the play written and directed by Samir Gulamov was held on November 9, 2021.The stage conductor and music composer of this play is Honored Art Worker Fakhraddin Atayev, stage designer Vusal Rahimli, stage balletmaster Honored Artist Leyla Aghayeva, concertmaster Kamil Hasanov.

It is talked about the desire of sick people in the rear of the Patriotic War in September-October 2020to go to the front in the play “Close as Breath”. Vatan’s heart is sick, Azer has asthma.But, they go to the Mobilization Service and go to war sometimes by begging, sometimes demanding, laughing and singing.Hundreds of our patriotic sons say goodbye to their mothers saying “don’t cry if I die” and go to war.

Vatan, who settled in Nakhchivanwhen he was forcibly exiled from his native Lachin 29 years ago, went to protect his motherland.Brave and proud mother Lachin blesses her child and sends him off to battle.This is the mother who says, “If you are shot in the back, my milk is forbidden for you!”

Mother Lachinis waiting for her son and believes that Vatan will return one day.Just as our homeland Karabakh returned after 30 years.My son will also return.One day mother Lachin had just dozed when her son Vatan came to her dream with his martyred comrades and said: Don’t worry about us!Our

place is much more comfortable than there! These words are mother Lachin's last consolation!

Azer, who returned from the war as a veteran, is mother Lachin's neighbor. He often visits mother Lachin, takes care of her, does not let her stay alone. Here is the appreciation given to the martyrs and the martyr's mother in Azerbaijan!

Amrah Dadashov (Vatan), Gulnara Abdullayeva (Lachin), Ibrahim Alizadeh (Azer), Nahida Orujova (Zarifa), who played the main roles in the play, play their characters with their inner feelings and sincerity.

People's Artist Azer Pasha Nematov is the author and stage producer of the play "Victorious Way", which was dedicated to the historical victory of our people in the 44-Day Patriotic War and premiered on May 28, 2022 by the Azerbaijan State Academic National Drama Theater. The stage design of the play was done by Honored Culture Worker Ilham Elkhanoglu and the music by People's Artist Siyavush Karimi.

The play stands out for its unusualness. While the spectators were in the lobby, the country's leader, Commander-in-Chief Ilham Aliyev's information about the front area was sounding. The actors among the spectators entered the hall and went on the stage with shouts "Give us weapons!", "Send us to the front!"

Azer Pasha Nematov, the author of the work, conveys the events happening in the country in the example of 4 families. These four families represent millions of people. There are also representatives of minority nations here. Spectators follow the events with about 30 participants eagerly. Video footages are also used on stage. The Supreme Commander-in-Chief's speeches, rocket firing on our cities, the liberation of Shusha from the occupation and the scenes of soldiers climbing steep rocks in the finale were shown in these video footages.

The roles are performed by Nureddin Mehdikhanli, Hijran Nasirova, Elchin Efendi, Ali Nur, Matanat Atakishiyeva, Elnar Garayev, Khadija Novruzlu, Ilaha Hasanova, Anar Heybatov, Ilyas Ahmadov, Afat Mammadova, Ayshad Mammadov and others.

At the same time, the Azerbaijan State Puppet Theater named after A. Shaig presented a stage play based on Zahid Khalil's verse play "The Bell of Victory" to the spectators on November 29, 2022. The production director of the play is Honored Artist Gurban Masimov, production artist Ravana Yagubova, music setting is by Hamida Rustamova. Music pieces

selected from the works by the genius composer Fikret Amirov created a beautiful harmony in the one-part wordless performance. Each director makes certain changes to the dramaturgical text. Director Gurban Masimov turned the character of the Aghsaggal (Goja) (Old man) in the play into the leading character of the performance. Although it is more difficult and responsible to perform alone on the stage during a mono performance, Rahim Rahimov, the leading actor of the theater who plays the character of the Goja, coped with this task skillfully.

The relationship of the events in the play between the past and the present in terms of time was also reflected in the stage arrangement. Goja's memories, martyr's father, were presented to the spectators through puppets in the background. The Khan's daughter in the background, khari-bulbul (*Ophrys sphegodes subsp. taurica*), crane and other elements on the stage that did not adapt to a foreign land created love for the homeland in the spectators.

The bell of the long-silenced telephone – the Victory bell – was ringing in the finale. Goja, who was eagerly waiting for news from his grandson, began to speak after the “Victory Bell”, breaking the silence. The word “Jan baba” (“Dear Grandpa”) that came out of his mouth for the first and last time sounded even more majestic under the sound of music.

The Aghdam State Drama Theater, one of our regional theaters, showed Nadir Gadimli's “Voice from Shusha” in the production by Karim Hasanov on May 6, 2023. The work talked about the heroism and war path of Yashar Huseynov, the chief ensign and who hoisted the first flag in Shusha, during the 44-day Patriotic War. Nadir Gadimli also created the character of his brother Fuzuli Huseynov, who was martyred in the First Karabakh War, in the play.

Mushfig Garayev designed the stage of the play, and Azer Shukurov arranged the music. Elmir Humbatov (Ahad kishi-father) and Nurana Aliyeva (Zarnigar-mother), Farhad Farhadzadeh (Yashar), Hakim Jafarli (Karim), Jamal Zamanov (Farman) and Ikhtiyar Mammadov (the ghost of Martyr Fuzuli) performed their roles with longing for the homeland and sufferings of the homeland.

When the curtain opens, we see black and white photos of the martyrs of the First Karabakh War on the stage. There is a photo of Fuzuli, Yashar's martyred brother, among them.

The only outstanding point in the play is Yashar's determination to win despite the heavy losses, who does not lose his fighting spirit, who says “I will

hoist our flag in Shusha”, who is ready to die for the Motherland at any time, and his friend Farman. Each character has his own truth, his own pain, his own hatred for the enemy. The mother has been looking after her son in tears for years. A father, who stooped because of his son’s pain, tries to calm her, saying, “He is not only ours, but the son of this hand, dear, don’t cry”. The performance, which ended with the hoist of the flag on the symbolic Shusha fortress, had its emotional finale after the real hero came out of the spectators and went up to the stage.

Plays on the theme of Karabakh have been staged in other theaters of our country. The play “Missiya” (“Mission”) written by Mubariz Hamidov and directed by Firudin Maharramov was presented to the spectators at the Sumgayit State Drama Theater (10.11.2021), the play “Haqqın 44 günü” (“44 Days of Justice”) written and directed by Anar Babanlı at the Lankaran State Drama Theater (16.09.2022), the play “Azad Şuşa” (“The Liberated Shusha”) by S. İbrahimli in the production by Karim Hasanov staged at Aghdam State Drama Theater (13.09.2022), the play “İlham ətirli Zəfər” (“Inspirational Victory”) by Rafiq Rahimli staged at Gusar State Lezgi Drama Theater (09.03.2022).

If the works staged at Azerbaijani theaters reflected people’s cries, pain and hope for the future before the Victory that we won in the 44-Day Patriotic War, after the Victory Day, these plays are a source of people’s pride and ignite the love of building and creating even more. Many festivals and competitions were organized on this occasion. On November 1, 2021, the Ministry of Culture and the Teatro.az art portal held a Festival of 4.4 Short Plays on the occasion of the anniversary of our historic Victory in the 44-Day Patriotic War. Due to the long and boring pandemic period, the Festival plays were shown online in a 15-minute video format. 22 plays were presented to the festival by 11 state, 6 private theaters and 5 independent men of art from Baku and regions [4].

Plays reflecting the brilliant victory of our army and dedicated to the memory of our martyrs were performed on the stage of the Azerbaijan State Academic Musical Theater from November 1 to 5. Besides state theaters, independent theaters also participated in the festival, and 3 of the 22 plays on the theme of Karabakh, war and victory presented to the festival were awarded by the jury.

The 3rd place at the festival was awarded to the play “The Last Meeting”, authored and directed by Tarlan Abdullayev, a young director of

the Lankaran State Drama Theater. The character of “The Last Meeting”, one of the most touching plays, does not want to live because her husband was martyred in the Second Karabakh War. But when she found out that she was pregnant, she decided to give birth to her child and raise him happily by living with her husband’s dreams. Guler Karimli and Sayad Aliyev played the roles in the play.

The 2nd place of the festival was given to the play “44”, written and directed by Zaur Aliyev, the director of the Azerbaijan State Academic Musical Theater. Irana Karimova and Mahammad Abdullayev, the unspoken characters of Z. Aliyev’s play “44”, were able to convey their pain and bitterness to the spectators with musical language and body movements.

The grand prize of the festival was awarded to the play “Neighbor” written and directed by Nihad Gulamzadeh, the director of the inclusive ASA Theater. The events are taking place in one of our regions that were occupied 30 years ago. Our national army liberates the next village in the Second Patriotic War. An Armenian family occupied the house of their Azerbaijani neighbor and lives there. The son of this family escaped from the occupier Armenian army and came home. They ran after hearing that our soldiers liberated the village. At that time, a young Azerbaijani officer enters the house and it turns out that this is the house where he was born. Although the Armenians lied to him and wanted to kill him, but they were shot by Azerbaijani soldiers; the treacherous, evil inner faces of the Armenians were revealed once again.

At the same time as the 4.4 Festival of Short Plays, the Union of Theater Workers started the festival of plays “Azerbaijan – the Winner” in our country [3].

The plays of the festival were presented on the Abbas Mirza Sharifzade’s stage of the Academic National Drama Theater and on the big stage of the Union of Theater Workers of Azerbaijan. The spectators watched “Ticket to Heaven” (author and director İlhamə Əhmədova) by Baku Children and Youth Theater, “The Value of Happiness” by Sahib Mammadov and Raulya Türkkən as an independent project and “Genghis Epos” (author Abdulla Gurbani, director Faiq Kərdəşov) by Gusar Lezgi Drama Theater at the festival, which lasted until November 5.

Conclusion. The glorious victory won by our country during the 44-Day Patriotic War, the bravery of our martyrs and their incomparable heroism were talked about in each of these plays. We say goodbye to you with the

hope of preparing plays on the theme of Karabakh written after “Victory Day” in our lands liberated from occupation: Shusha, Aghdam and Fuzuli theaters.

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Mələhət Ağayeva (Azərbaycan)

“ZƏFƏR GÜNÜ”NDƏN SONRA AZƏRBAYCAN TEATRLARINDA QARABAĞ MÖVZULU TAMAŞALARIN SƏHNƏ XÜSUSİYYƏTLƏRİ

Məqalədə “Zəfər günü”ndən sonra Qarabağ mövzusunda olan əsərlərin Azərbaycan teatrlarındakı səhnə təcəssümündən danışılır. Zəfər günündən sonra bu tamaşalar insanların qürur mənbəyi olaraq, onları daha da qurub-yaratmaq eşiqlə alovlandırır. Zəfərdən sonra oynanan Azərbaycan Dövlət Akademik Milli Dram Teatrında Azər Paşa Nemətovun müəllifi və rejissorluğu ilə göstərilən “Zəfər yolu” tamaşasında, Azərbaycan Dövlət Akademik Musiqili Teatrında Samir Qulamovun müəllifi və rejissorluğu ilə göstərilən “Bir nəfəs qədər” tamaşası və Sumqayıt Dövlət Dram Teatrında Mübariz Həmidovun müəllifi və Firudin Məhərrəmovun rejissorluğu ilə “Missiya”, Lənkəran Dövlət Dram Teatrında Anar Babanlının müəllifi və rejissorluğu ilə “Haqqın 44 günü”, Ağdam Dövlət Dram Teatrı Kərim Həsənovun quruluşunda S.İbrahimlinin “Azad Şuşa”, Qusar Dövlət Ləzgi Dram Teatrı Rafiq Rəhimlinin “İlham ətirli Zəfər” şəhidlərə, qazilərə və şəhid ailələrinə verilən qiymətdən danışılırdı.

Açar sözlər: Qarabağ mövzusu, Vətən müharibəsi, Zəfər günü, qazandığı tarixi qələbə, şəhidlərimizin xatirəsinə.

Малахат Агаева (Азербайджан)

СЦЕНИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СПЕКТАКЛЕЙ НА ТЕМУ КАРАБАХА В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКИХ ТЕАТРАХ ПОСЛЕ «ДНЯ ПОБЕДЫ»

В статье рассказывается о сценическом воплощении в азербайджанских театрах произведений на тему Карабаха после “Дня Победы”. После Дня Победы эти спектакли, как источник гордости людей, зажигают их еще большей любовью к созиданию. В спектакле “Путь Победы”, написанном и поставленном Азером Паша оглы Неметовым и сыгранном после победы в Азербайджанском Государственном Академическом Национальном Драматическом Театре, в спектакле “До последнего дыхания”, написанном и поставленном Самиром Гуламовым в Азербайджанском Государственном Академическом Музыкальном театре, в спектакле “Миссия”, написанном Мубаризом Гамидовым и поставленном Фирудином Магеррамовым в Сумгаитском Государственном Драматическом Театре, в спектакле “44 дня Возмездия”, написанном и поставленном Анаром Бабанлы в Ленкоранском Государственном Драматическом Театре, в спектакле “Свободная Шуша” С. Ибрагимли, поставленном Керимом Гасановым в Агдамском Государственном Драматическом Театре, а также в спектакле “Победа с духом Ильхама”, поставленном Рафигом Рагимли в Гусарском Государственном Лезгинском Драматическом Театре, рассказывается о том, как ценят шехидов, ветеранов и семей шехидов, и проводится изучение и исследование таких спектаклей.

Ключевые слова: тема Карабаха, Отечественная война, День Победы, историческая победа, в память наших шехидов.